

LINGUISTICS. LINGUISTIC METHODS AND ITS SECTIONS

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Annotation: This article includes sections related to the field of linguistics and methods of linguistic analysis. This article covers all the sections and describes the methods separately.

Keywords: linguistics, private linguistics, fragmentary method, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, historical-comparative method, substitution method, distributive method, component method, transformational method, statistical analysis method, phonetic-phonological level, lexical level, a method of meaning scale analysis.

Linguistics is the study of language, its social significance and functions, and its internal structure; about the laws of its operation and the historical development and classification of certain languages. Linguistics is a multifaceted science because language is a very complex multifaceted phenomenon. Linguistics as a science is divided into general and specific. Within the framework of general linguistics, typological linguistics is distinguished. Its task is to compare unrelated languages.

Private linguistics is the science of individual languages, for example, Russian studies is the science of the Russian language, Ukrainian studies is the science of the Ukrainian language, and so on. Private linguistics should be studied synchronously (the study of the facts of language at the same time) and diachrony (the study of the facts of language in their development). Each science has a field of knowledge and a certain number of scientific tasks. Let us define the scope of tasks of linguistics as a science.

1. Learn the origin and essence of language.
2. Consider the structure of language.
3. The study of language as a whole system in which all members are interconnected and interdependent, rather than a collection of individual facts or words.
4. Consider the development of language in relation to the development of society (the process of the emergence of both)
5. To study the origin and development of writing.
6. Classification of languages, ie combining them according to the principle of similarity; how different German and English languages are; Russian, Ukrainian and Belarusian.

A comprehensive analysis of language, which is the field of study of linguistics, requires methods appropriate to the development of science. Any method that analyzes each area must meet the following requirements.

1. The method must be objective. The result should be the same regardless of the time and place of application of the method. Subjective approaches negatively affect the value of the method.
2. The method should be consistent and based on clear concepts.
3. The method should be universal, it should be able to analyze the main divisions of the industry (at least four).
4. The method should be as simple as possible. There are several methods used in linguistics.

There are two types of these methods: a) general methods. b) methods of linguistic analysis. These methods work in conjunction with each other and provide specific conclusions. General methods are the methods used by all aspects of the social sphere. In particular, the methods of analysis from general to specific, from private to general, analysis-synthesis, from simple to complex are used in almost all areas. Linguistic analysis methods are unique to linguistics and serve to draw scientific conclusions about the science. In modern linguistics, the following methods are used for linguistic analysis; - part of speech method; - historical-comparative method; - substitution (substitution) method; - distributive method; - method of disassembly; - transformation method; - method of statistical analysis; is a method of analyzing the scope of meaning. The part of speech method has been used since the early days of linguistics. According to this method, sentences are divided into parts. It is based on the function of the word in the sentence. Here's how to do a piecemeal analysis. 1. The main parts of speech (possessive and participle) are divided into secondary parts (complement, determiner, case). 2. The function of the parts of speech determines which phrase is used. 3. The grammatical forms (morphological categories) of the words that come as part of the sentence are explained. This method only works in the syntax section. The difficulty of using this method is observed in almost all languages. The historical-comparative method is the primary method based on comparative-historical linguistics. This method is formed by comparing the diversity of world languages, their similarities and differences. This method solves the following problems: 1. Determining whether languages are related or non-related by comparing their characteristics and similarities with other languages. 2. Comparative study of cognate languages to determine the common genetic basis for them; using a retrospective comparison method to study this analysis. This is done by comparing the current state of languages to their historical aspects. 3. The evolution of languages is studied, that is, it is possible to make a comparative analysis of the development of languages to their current state. Such a comparison is called a

prospective comparison. Historical inscriptions serve as a starting point. Using this method, a family of languages is determined. For example, the Indo-European language family, the Turkic language family, the Mongolian language family, and so on. Language families are further subdivided according to certain characteristics. In particular, Turkish languages are divided into about thirty groups. The substitution method is based on the substitution method. The resulting methodological changes are analyzed by replacing them with language units and other alternatives that are in a certain place in the speech. This method determines the place of synonyms, antonyms and homonyms in the lexical system. The distributive method analyzes the ability of language units to interact with other units in the speech process. Distribution can be interpreted as a "syntactic possibility." For example, the ability of a word, morpheme, or phoneme to interact with another word, morpheme, or phoneme, is called the distribution of these units. There are morphological, syntactic and lexical-semantic types of distribution. Morphological distribution is the ability of a word in one category to interact with a word in another category: noun with adjective, verb with form. The method of subdivision analyzes any whole, in particular, a sentence, as if it consisted of parts in a relationship between the ruler and the subordinate. This method applies at the grammatical level: morphology and syntax. The transformation method is the most perfect of all modern methods. This method is characterized by the ability to explain the syntactic process in language. Statistical analysis is used at all levels of language and is therefore universal. This method accurately shows the level of use of language units and language events in speech. The semantic scale analysis method analyzes the lexical meaning of a word by dividing it into separate semantic aspects. This method is important for clarifying the meaning of polysemous words. In general, the role of linguistic methods in determining the most general and specific laws of linguistics is invaluable. In linguistics, the department of sciences traditionally organized at this stage of the development of linguistic sciences. 1) The sciences of the internal structure of language, or "internal linguistics." This group of disciplines includes: phonetics and phonology; grammar is divided into morphology and syntax (sometimes with emphasis on morphology); lexicology (focusing on phraseology); semantics (sometimes emphasis on semantics); style; typology. 2) The sciences of the historical development of language. This group primarily includes language history: historical grammar (sometimes broadly synonymous with language history); comparative-historical grammar; history of literary languages; etymology. 3) The sciences of the spread of language in society or "foreign linguistics": dialectology, linguistic geography; regional linguistics; sociolinguistics. 4) Disciplines dealing with the study of complex problems and emerging at the intersection of disciplines: psycholinguistics, mathematical linguistics; engineering linguistics

(sometimes understood as an applied science); applied linguistics: lexicography; experimental phonetics; linguistic statistics; paleography; writing history, etc.

A phrase is a part of speech that is separated by a complete pause with a single intonation. Phonetic transcription is used to express pronunciation and is widely used in foreign language dictionaries. The reflection of each pronounced sound is the primary function of phonetic transcription. Transcription can be based on any alphabet. Some special sounds are marked with diacritical marks, additional characters from other alphabets, and inverted symbols. Phonetic transcription is important in learning a foreign language. Phonemic transcription is often used in grammar books to show the morphological structure of examples, because in such cases the word structure is more important than the pronunciation; this transcription is basically to show the phonemes always with the same sign, regardless of where they are used. Inflected languages are languages that are difficult to distinguish between stem morphemes and affix morphemes. Characteristics: - One affix has several meanings - an affix can indicate a person, time and number at the same time. - The affix can have several variants - a change of sounds can be observed when affixes are added to the stem and base. - It is difficult to draw the line between root and base, base and grammatical affixes. Because language is a powerful tool for influencing the listener, the science of linguistics is inextricably linked with literature, and this has given rise to the science of linguopoetics. Linguopoetics studies the artistic and aesthetic functions of linguistic units used in works of art, the connotative function of language. Literary language as a comprehensive object has the property of being divided into functionally graded parts, fragments. In practice, however, only certain fragments of this object are given to the analysis of artistic speech. Hence, artistic speech is a broad concept, and the language of a work of art is a view, a fragment, of artistic speech. Since it includes the expressive function of language, it covers the artistic-aesthetic function of all level units of the language system. Therefore, linguopoetics is divided into such types as phonetic poetics, lexical poetics, syntactic poetics. The task of linguopoetics is to study these areas separately and to shed light on their interrelationships as well.

Phonetic-phonological level

- At this level, it is studied that the same sounds occur in the repetition of the same syllables, mainly (repetition of the same vowels), alliteration (repetition of the same consonants), and serve as a means of generalization.

Lexical level

- It is understood that lexemes are used in a figurative sense (for example, the word is used in the sense of stage in the poem "Ascend from the shoots of puberty every second").

Due to the emergence of language in speech activity, speech activity is the object of study in both linguistics and psychology.

The term psycholinguistics was first used in 1946 by the American psychologist N. Pronko and has been widely used since the 1950s. However, its roots go back to the current of psychologism (founder G. Steintal), which emerged in the XIX century on the basis of comparative-historical linguistics. He sought to create a social, ethnic psychology, emphasizing the expression of the people's spirit in language.

The object of study of psycholinguistics includes:

- To study the mechanism of formation of speech activity
- To study the process of formation of children's speech
- Exploring the relationship between speaker and listener in specific speech situations

- Learning and managing the information transfer function of speech

Ethnolinguistics

The term ethnolinguistics is derived from the Greek word "ethnos" for people, tribe, and originated in the 1970s due to the intensification of the study of the language, culture, and customs of American Indians. It is known that in the history of a nation, every event that happens in the way of life, every tradition is reflected in its language, so there is an integral connection between the language and the truth that owns it. Toponyms and ethnonyms cannot be studied without knowing the history of the people, and ethnography also provides valuable material for linguistics. The need to study ethnoculture, ethnopsychological factors in the practice and development of language has given rise to the direction of ethnolinguistics in linguistics.

Formation of ethnolinguistics

- The services of the American linguist, ethnographer F. Boas in the formation of ethnolinguistics as an independent linguistic direction were great. He and his followers studied the Indian language in relation to the interaction of languages and cultures, bilingualism.

- In the first period of this direction, more ethnographic issues were addressed, only from the 1920s onwards, the linguistic side of the problem was emphasized.

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